

ECONOMY

DIGITALIZATION OF EDUCATION IN THE CONTEXT OF FORMING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF A GRADUATE OF A HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTION IN THE LABOR MARKET

Bezuglaya V.,

Candidate of Economics, Associate Professor of the Department of Economics and Accounting, Faculty of Economics and Law "BIP – University of Law and Social-Information Technologies", Minsk

Kostyukevich E.

ME, Head of Marketing and Management Section, Department of Theoretical and Applied Economics, Faculty of Economics and Law, Baranovichi State University, Baranovichi

Abstract

The article summarizes the factors of the national digital strategy. The basic principles of the digital economy are formulated. The main directions of the digital transformation of the education system have been identified and a competency-based model of digital education has been developed.

Keywords: Digitalization, education, education, competitiveness, graduate, labor market, model of digital education.

In modern conditions, digitalization is the main direction of sustainable development of the country, economy and social relations.

The world is currently experiencing a digital revolution, which entails significant consequences both for the global economy as a whole and for individual countries. According to forecasts, there will be an increase in the speed of the introduction of technological innovations and their dissemination. Digital technologies and their applications are spreading around the world faster than during previous waves of technological innovations, and completely change all human activity [1].

When developing a national digital strategy, it is important to consider the following factors:

- The speed of development and implementation of technological innovations.
- Rationalization of consumer behavior.
- Development of e-commerce.
- Optimization of business processes.
- Personalization of goods and services.
- Reducing transaction costs and information asymmetry.
- Active involvement of human capital in economic and social processes.

All these factors optimize the work of each individual employee of the organization, due to which personal performance is considered as the main criterion for the competitiveness of an employee in the labor market. To be successful, it is necessary to be fast and flexible: to change not when there is an opportunity, but when there is a need, to have a certain set of competencies acquired in the learning process.

Higher education is a source of a highly skilled workforce, so it is not surprising that in the context of the increasing pace of digital transformation of society, universities all around the world are trying to use the most effective technologies and teaching methods [2].

However, despite the significant advantages of the development of digitalization, there are certain difficulties associated with the modernization of the educa-

tional system in order to improve the training of qualified personnel, in accordance with the fundamental principles of the functioning of the digital economy.

The main principles of the digital economy are:

1. Digitized information has become a strategic resource, and network technologies have become the main organizing principle of the economy and society as a whole. A new generation of digital technologies is now generating unprecedented amounts of data and providing the tools needed to exploit this asset. With all this, the concept of "information explosion" as an avalanche-like increase in the mass of various information in modern society was born in 1975.

2. The digital economy, along with the ever-growing range of tangible and intangible economic activities, follows the principles of increasing profitability.

3. New business models are emerging to take advantage of bilateral markets. A bilateral market is a meeting place for two agents who interact through an intermediary or platform. The participation of both parties is fundamental to the development and success of each platform and to a deep understanding of the pricing strategies pursued by market participants. In the context of the digital economy, a bilateral market is understood as online platforms. For example, remote job search platforms upwork.com, kwork.ru.

4. A new model of industrial production ("Industry 4.0") includes short production cycles of mass goods, global fragmentation of value chains, creation of production capacity networks and blurring of boundaries between producers, sellers and consumers based on decentralization, automation and artificial intelligence [3].

For example, when assessing the level of the development of the digital economy based on the index of international digital competitiveness, among other indicators that form the foundation of the digital economy, education and training are taken into account [4]. As noted in the article by A. Kosenkov [5], "the lack of a sufficient number of qualified personnel and underestimation of the role of the development of digital competencies among the population" is one of the limiting

factors in the development of digitalization, which the education system is called upon to eliminate [6].

The National Strategy for Sustainable Development of the Republic of Belarus until 2035 [7] actualizes the issue of digitalization of the education system in the direction of increasing the level of digital literacy of future workers in the learning process in order to meet the needs of the digital economy in personnel with digital professional competencies and knowledge that form the competitiveness of modern specialists in labor market. In the context of global digitalization, the introduction of digital technologies into the educational system, the creation of new learning formats, the updating of the content of educational programs and teaching methods are among the defining directions for the development of modern education.

In the current economic conditions, representatives of business and the real sector of the economy note the low efficiency of the traditional system of education in higher education institutions, also due to the specifics of the contingent of students (Generation Z) [8], who were born and grew up in the era of postmodernism and globalization, i.e. in a world where opportunities are endless, and there is not enough time for everything, and therefore it is the digitalization of the educational system that will make learning more effective for them and allow them to quickly evaluate and sift through huge amounts of information.

According to Global Digital 2021, the digital sphere is characterized by the following data:

1. Global population: as of early 2021, the world population was 7.83 billion. Since the beginning of 2020, the world population has increased by more than 80 million people.

2. Mobile Devices: today, 5.22 billion people use a mobile phone – 66.6% of the world's population.

3. Internet: in January 2021, 4.66 billion people worldwide use the Internet, which is 7.3% more than last year.

4. Social Media: in 2021, 53.6% of the global population are using social media [9].

The basis for the development of an innovative educational system is the widespread use of modern information and computer technologies, continuous professional development of teaching staff, the involvement of teachers and students in scientific research, the

interaction of educational institutions with organizations in the real sector of the economy, cultural and ideological education of students.

The main directions of digital transformation of the education system are:

- The use of a hybrid form of education, including elements of full-time offline education, elements of distance education and cloud services.

- Introduction into the curricula of all specialties of higher education institutions of disciplines aimed at increasing the competitiveness of graduates and related to the acquisition of competencies in the field of informatization, computerization and digitalization.

- The use, along with traditional forms of education, of a network form of higher education, which in modern conditions provides for distance learning on the basis of several educational institutions, the active use of information resources in the educational process. Several institutions of higher education create inter-university platforms for the exchange of information in order to save money and expand the scale of joint educational, scientific and educational activities, which contributes to the globalization of higher education and a significant increase in the competitiveness of future specialists in the labor market.

- Search for new digital tools and methods to increase the competitiveness of higher education institutions in the global market of educational services. In connection with the aggravation of competition, the issue of increasing the effectiveness of the marketing activities of higher education institutions has recently been updated. Marketing of educational services is expanding and developing already in the virtual space, with the help of digital Internet technologies and involves the active use of traditional and new promotion tools on the global Internet.

- Development of digital marketing tools to promote educational institutions and educational services (websites, search engines, communication tools, social networks, mobile devices, television, radio, and other forms of digital communications).

Competency-based model of digital education is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Competency-based model of digital education

The advantages of digital education are:

- increasing the accessibility of educational resources, including for people with disabilities.
- quick and easy adaptation to changing environmental conditions.
- high competitiveness of graduates in the labor market.
- the possibility, if necessary, of a quick transition to distance learning.
- simplifying the interaction of a higher education institution with the external environment (network education, guest lectures, interaction with personnel customers, career guidance, etc.).
- effective personalized interaction with each student through the introduction of personal electronic cabinets of students and teachers.
- simplification and improvement of the quality of workflow of higher education institutions through the use of a single information environment.
- acceleration of the integration processes of the education system of the Republic of Belarus into the world information and educational space.

The impact of digitalization of education on the competitiveness of graduates in the labor market is due to the actualization of the training of highly qualified specialists who not only have a certain set of knowledge, skills and competencies, but are also able to flexibly apply them in the digital economy.

At the moment of transition to a digital economy, the most relevant is the formation of digital competencies among students of various specialties, teaching them how to use information computer technologies in various areas of their future work, skills to adapt to rapidly changing environmental conditions, the ability to process large amounts of information using ICT tools, and continuous learning and self-learning.

In addition, the introduction of digital technologies into the system of modern education in the long term ensure the competitiveness of educational institutions of the Republic of Belarus in the domestic and foreign markets of educational services, significantly improve the quality and accessibility of education (distance learning), which in turn will increase the attractiveness for potential consumers and accelerate integration into the international educational space.

References

1. Carl Dahlmann, Sam Miley and Martin Wermelinger. Leveraging the Digital Economy for Developing Countries// OECD DEVELOPMENT CENTER – №334 – 2016 – 80 C. <https://doi.org/10.1787/4adffb24-en>
2. Stefan Stieglitz, Christian Meske, Raimund Vogl, Dominik Rudolph. Demand for Cloud Services as an Infrastructure in Higher Education 35th International Conference on Information Systems (ICIS) At: Auckland, New Zealand, 2014 [Electronic resource]. – 2014. – Access mode https://www.researchgate.net/publication/266030309_Demand_for_Cloud_Services_as_an_Infrastructure_in_Higher_Education - Access date: 11/17/2021.
3. Plotnikov, A. V. Basic principles of the digital economy concept // Moscow Economic Journal – No. 5 (2) – 2018. – P. 330-335 (printed in Russian)
4. Bris, A. The IMD World Digital Competitiveness Ranking / A. Bris, J. Caballero, Ch. Cabolis // IMD [Electronic resource]. – 2019. – Mode of Access: <https://www.imd.org/research-knowledge/articles/the-imd-world-digital-competitiveness-ranking>. – Date of access: 11/17/2021.
5. Kosenkov, A. "IT-country": the reverse side of the digitalization of Belarus // Eurasia expert [Electronic resource]. – 2019. – Access mode <https://eurasia.expert/it-strana-obratnaya-storona-tsifrovizatsii-belarusi>. – Access date: 11/17/2021. (printed in Russian)
6. Divina, T. V. Opportunities and prospects for the use of digital transformation in education / T.V. Divina, E.V. Maymina // Actual problems of economics and management. – 2020. – No. 55. – P. 38–48. (printed in Russian)
7. The concept of the National Strategy for Sustainable Development Republic of Belarus for the period up to 2035 // Official website of the Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Belarus [Electronic resource]. – Access mode: <https://www.economy.gov.by/uploads/files/ObsugdaemNPA/Kontseptsija-na-sajt.pdf>. – Access date: 11/17/2021. (printed in Russian)
8. Kovalev, M. M. Digital economy is a chance for Belarus: monograph. / M. M. Kovalev, G. G. Golovenchik. – Minsk: Ed. center of BSU, 2018. – 327 p. (printed in Russian)
9. We Are Social, Hootsuite Global Digital 2021 [Electronic resource]. – 2014. – Access mode: <https://www.web-canape.ru/business/vsya-statistika-interneta-i-socsetej-na-2021-god-cifry-i-trendy-v-mire-iv-rossii/>. – Access date: 11/17/2021